

Lifestyle Intervention Strategy to Treat Diabetes in Older Adults: A Randomized Controlled Trial

Older adults, particularly those over 65, have the highest incidence of diabetes. This is linked to various factors such as lack of physical activity and increased obesity, both of which contribute to the development of the disease. As a result, diabetes has become a significant public health issue. With age, there is a decline in metabolic and physical functions, which further increases the risk of diabetes. For older adults, weight loss interventions are considered controversial due to the increased risk of bone fragility and other issues related to the aging process. Therefore, the therapeutic approach must be tailored to the patient's age, taking into account specific health needs and risks. Studies have shown that lifestyle changes, involving both older and younger individuals, lead to improvements in physical and metabolic functions. Importantly, lifestyle interventions also contribute to improved insulin sensitivity and a reduction in metabolic complications. A randomized controlled trial conducted among older adults with diabetes found that lifestyle interventions (including changes in diet and physical activity) led to improvements in glycemic control, body composition, and quality of life. Another key aspect is the improvement of insulin sensitivity. Lack of physical activity and excess body fat contribute to insulin resistance, a major mechanism in the development of type 2 diabetes. In older adults, insulin resistance may also be due to reduced function of pancreatic beta cells, which are responsible for insulin production. Studies indicate that lifestyle interventions can improve the response of pancreatic cells to hyperglycemia, leading to better blood glucose control. With aging, the production of glucagon by pancreatic alpha cells increases, which can contribute to hyperglycemia by stimulating glucose production in the liver. Therefore, reducing body fat and improving physical fitness are crucial for improving metabolic control, particularly in glucose regulation. In conclusion, lifestyle interventions for older adults, such as increasing physical activity and reducing body fat, can lead to improved insulin sensitivity, better glycemic control, and overall improvement in metabolic health.

Figure 1

The primary outcome was the change in HbA_{1c} from baseline to 1 year. Secondary outcomes were the changes in insulin sensitivity and secretion, glucose tolerance variables, body weight and composition, and physical function and quality of life.

Safety was assessed continuously through adverse event reports, physical examination, vital signs, and blood chemistries. To reduce the risk of severe hypoglycemia during intensive weight loss, the study physician adjusted the dose of insulin or insulin secretagogues using a prespecified algorithm; otherwise, all diabetes and medical care was conducted by the participant's own clinician. Of the 167 volunteers assessed for eligibility, 27 were excluded because they did not meet the inclusion criteria or declined to participate.

Table 1

Baseline characteristics are presented in table 1. Approximately 40% of participants were of Black race. Participants were taking different types of diabetes medications, and almost half were on insulin therapy. There was a high prevalence of mild frailty associated with coexisting conditions and use of chronic medications.

Figure 2 and Table 2

There was a substantial mean $\pm$ SE decrease in body weight in the ILI group (-8.4 ± 0.6 kg) but not HL group (-0.3 ± 0.6 kg). The time course of weight loss is shown in figure 2. In accordance with the weight loss, fat mass and visceral adipose tissue decreased in the ILI group but did not change in HL group. Likewise, LBM decreased in the ILI group but was maintained in the HL group (-1.7 ± 0.3 vs. 0.2 ± 0.3 kg).

AUTHORS

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Bryan Jiang - comes from Houston. In 2017 he joined the Baylor Endocrinology faculty after completing residency and fellowship training here at Baylor College of Medicine. He is a clinician-educator who holds special interests in quality improvement as well as the treatment of metabolic bone diseases such as osteoporosis. He devotes the majority of his time seeing patients within the Harris Health System. He received Endocrinology Board Certification and Internal Medicine Board Certification. Bryan Jiang's main professional interests are Osteoporosis, Sarcopenia, Quality Improvement.

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Dennis T. Villareal - physician-scientist with specialty training in geriatrics and endocrinology. He has extensive clinical and research experience in examining the impact of lifestyle interventions in reversing frailty in older adults with obesity. His clinical and translational laboratories involve hormonal, nutritional, and behavioral/lifestyle interventions to retard or reverse the metabolic and physical complications of aging, including sarcopenic obesity and type 2 diabetes. He is dedicated to research designed to inform practice guidelines with respect to optimal treatment strategies for older adults with obesity. **His H-index is 68.**

JOURNAL

Diabetes Care is one of the leading journals in the field of endocrinology and diabetes research. Its impact is far-reaching, as it publishes high-quality research that shapes clinical practice and informs public health policies around the world. The journal's scope is broad, addressing a wide array of topics such as:

1. **Clinical Trials:** The journal features original research on clinical trials that explore new treatments, medications, and interventions for managing diabetes. This includes studies on insulin therapies, oral medications, GLP-1 agonists, SGLT2 inhibitors, and more.
2. **Epidemiology and Public Health:** Diabetes Care provides valuable insights into the global prevalence and risk factors associated with diabetes. It often publishes large-scale epidemiological studies that examine the social, genetic, and environmental determinants of diabetes.
3. **Diabetes Complications:** It publishes research on the prevention and management of diabetes-related complications, including cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, and foot issues, which are critical areas in diabetes care.
4. **Innovations in Technology:** The journal covers advances in diabetes technology, such as continuous glucose monitoring (CGM), insulin pumps, and the latest in artificial pancreas systems. It also explores the role of telemedicine and digital health tools in improving patient outcomes.
5. **Guidelines and Standards of Care:** Diabetes Care regularly publishes updates to the American Diabetes Association's Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes. These guidelines are essential for healthcare providers in managing diabetes and are regularly referenced in clinical practice.
6. **Basic and Translational Research:** The journal also features research that delves into the molecular mechanisms behind diabetes, including studies on insulin resistance, beta-cell dysfunction, and genetic predisposition. This research paves the way for potential breakthroughs in treatment.
7. **Prevention and Lifestyle:** Given the increasing prevalence of type 2 diabetes, Diabetes Care emphasizes the importance of prevention strategies, including lifestyle modifications, diet, exercise, and weight management programs, which are essential in combating the diabetes epidemic.
8. **Patient-Centered Care:** There is an increasing focus on patient engagement, education, and the psychosocial aspects of diabetes care.

The journal includes research on improving patient self-management, mental health considerations, and social determinants of health. The journal is highly influential, both in clinical practice and in shaping the direction of future research. Its readership includes not only healthcare professionals but also policymakers, researchers, and educators who are working to improve outcomes for people with diabetes. The high level of evidence-based content ensures that Diabetes Care remains an authoritative source for those looking to stay on top of the latest developments in diabetes care

Diabetes Care is designed to promote better patient care by serving the expanded needs of all health professionals committed to the care of patients with diabetes. Diabetes Care is also a journal for the health care practitioner that is intended to increase knowledge, stimulate research, and promote better management of people with diabetes. To achieve these goals, the journal publishes original research on human studies in the following categories: Clinical Care/Education/Nutrition/Psychosocial Research, Epidemiology/Health Services Research, Emerging Treatments and Technologies, Pathophysiology/Complications, and Cardiovascular and Metabolic Risk. The journal also publishes ADA statements, consensus reports, clinically relevant review articles, letters to the editor, and health/medical news or points of view. Topics covered are of interest to clinically oriented physicians, researchers, epidemiologists, psychologists, diabetes educators, and other health professionals. In order to make original research available faster than traditional print publishing allows, articles accepted for publication in Diabetes Care are published online ahead of print 5–6 weeks after acceptance, after copyediting, composition, and proofreading. All articles become freely accessible 12 months after the print publication date. In addition, the following are freely available immediately upon publication.

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